

PERCEPTION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATION**Burkhonov Shavqiddin**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the perception of preschool children as a separate branch of psychology in the context of globalization. Based on primary sources, it examines the laws of children's psychological development and the characteristics of perception in preschool-aged children.

Keywords: Globalization, perception, memory, attention, thinking, child psychology, psychodiagnostics, ontogenesis, phylogenesis, sensory, sensitive period, cognition, cognitive development, age dynamics, methods, principles.

Perception is the reflection of objects and phenomena through the direct influence of sensory organs, represented in the totality of their properties and components. It includes the individual's past experience in the form of ideas and knowledge.

Perception is the direct reflection of surrounding objects, events, or processes. It is a subjective image of an object, process, or phenomenon that directly affects an analyzer or a system of analyzers. Sometimes the term perception also refers to a system of actions directed toward sensations, namely the sensory-research activity of observation.

External phenomena affecting our sensory organs create subjective impressions in the form of sensations without any opposing activity from the subject toward the perceived influence.

Unlike sensations, perception always appears subjectively connected with reality existing outside us and organized in the form of objects. Sensations exist within us, whereas the perceived properties of objects and their images are localized in space. This characteristic feature distinguishing perception from sensations is called objectification. Another distinction between perception and sensations in developed forms is that the result of sensation is a certain feeling (for example, light, volume, balance, sweetness, etc.), while the result of perception is an image formed in human consciousness, including a complex of interconnected sensations related to a particular object, event, or process. In order to perceive a specific object, it is necessary to carry out some opposing activity aimed at studying, constructing, and improving its image. Individual sensations are, as it were, attached to specific analyzers, and for sensation to arise, it is sufficient for a stimulus to affect their peripheral organs — the receptors. The image formed as a result of the perception process implies interaction and the coordinated functioning of several analyzers simultaneously.

Thus, perception performs the function of a meaningful and designated synthesis (including decision-making) of various sensations obtained from integral objects or complex phenomena perceived as a whole. This synthesis appears in the form of an image of a specific object or phenomenon that develops during the process of active reflection.

The sensory image emerges as a result of the synthesis of sensations. According to Aleksei Nikolaevich Leontiev, this became possible in phylogenesis due to the transition of living beings from a homogeneous and objectively unformed environment to an objectively structured one.

Depending on the biological significance of the perceived object, one or another quality may become dominant, which determines the priority of a particular analyzer.

The image formed as a result of perception implies interaction and coordinated functioning of several analyzers at the same time. Depending on which analyzer functions more actively and processes more information, the most important features of the perceived object are distinguished, and different types of perception are identified. Accordingly, tactile, visual, and auditory perceptions are distinguished. In all types of perception, motor or kinesthetic sensations play a particularly important role, regulating the subject's actual relationship with the object according to the principle of feedback. In visual perception, along with actual visual sensations (color and light), kinesthetic sensations accompanying eye movements (accommodation, convergence, divergence, and tracking) are also integrated.

Similarly, in auditory perception, weak movements of the articulatory apparatus play an active role. It is characteristic of humans that their perceptual images incorporate the use of speech. Through verbal designation, it becomes possible to abstract and generalize the properties of objects.

Therefore, perception is the process and result of forming a subjective image of an object or phenomenon influencing the analyzer. The entire phylogenetic development of sensitivity demonstrates that the decisive factor in the development of sensitivity toward a particular stimulus is its biological significance, that is, its connection with life, behavior, and adaptation to the environment. Throughout life, while solving practical tasks, humans perceive the surrounding environment. Perceiving objects and people with whom one interacts, as well as the conditions in which one's activities occur, constitutes a necessary prerequisite for meaningful action. In perception, a person not only sees but also observes, not only hears but also listens; often a person actively selects an attitude that ensures adequate perception of the object. By perceiving, the individual performs a certain activity aimed at adapting the perceptual image to the object. Sensation is the sensory reflection of an object or phenomenon of objective reality that affects our senses.

Human perception is not merely a sensory image but also an awareness of an object distinguished from the environment and opposed to the subject. The possibility of perception presupposes not only the subject's ability to react to a sensory stimulus but also the awareness of the corresponding sensory quality as a property of a particular object. Perceiving an object presupposes not only the existence of an image but also a certain effective environment resulting from highly developed tonic activity of the cerebellum and cortex.

Further development of perception occurs in close connection with the development of various types of children's activities, including play, visual, constructive, labor activities, and elements of learning. By the age of four, perception acquires relative independence.

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